

Quartzes matter. Understanding the technological and behavioural complexity in quartz lithic assemblages.

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The application of the *Chaine opératoire* approach developed in the lithic studies during the last decades has overcome the assumed “archaic” character of the quartz lithic assemblages. These studies have gone beyond the informal appearance of the quartz artefacts in order to achieve a positive understanding of the technological strategies that ruled the management of this lithic resource by the prehistoric societies.

Because of its hardness, mechanical and physical properties macrocrystalline quartz was heavily used in the Pleistocene and Holocene lithic technologies. Besides, quartz is one of the most abundant minerals on Earth’s crust, usually related to Palaeozoic and granitic substrata, where the different varieties are available both on primary outcrops (quartz veins) and secondary deposits (alluvial or colluvial). Finally, its brightness and whitish colour make quartz a high perceivable resource in the territory, favouring its identification and collection.

However and despite its general presence in the archaeological record, lithic studies have traditionally regarded quartz as a second-rate lithic resource, its use strictly conditioned by the scarcity of better quality or cryptocrystalline rocks in the surrounding territories (Bordes, 1947; Mourre, 1996). Every now and then, a few studies were developed in those sites where quartz was the predominant raw material (i.e. Pei, 1932), or where notable tools were recovered (i.e. de Givenchy, 1923).

Quartz studies have had a late development within the lithic studies tradition. From the 1970’s onwards, the increase on the research activity and the impact of the processual approach of the *New Archaeology* led to the emergence of lithic studies focused on minority raw materials. Such studies lay the foundation of the

present day research (i.e. Holm and Knutsson, 1998; Moloney et al, 1996; Rodríguez-Rellán, 2015; Sternke et al., 2009). These first examples of quartz studies were conducted in those regions where this mineral was the predominant raw material. Thus, in Europe, we must highlight the pioneering studies developed in Scandinavia under an experimental, technological and functional perspective, thanks –in part– to the influx of the North American studies and researchers (Apel and Knutsson, 2006; Barber, 1981; Flenniken, 1981). These approaches carried out in the northernmost part of Europe contributed to the definition of the quartz technology in a very significant way (Broadbent, 1973; Callahan, 1987; K. Knutsson, 1988a, *inter alia*). Meanwhile, in France, the studies of the Middle and Upper Palaeolithic sites (Bracco, 1997b; Mourre, 1996 and references therein) allowed to detect the complexity of the techno-economical roles played by this resource within the prehistoric groups.

In recent years, the research has focused on the characterization of quartz from a petrographic, technological and functional point of view. In this sense, the experimental archaeology has been a very useful discipline for helping to achieve a complete understanding of the quartz lithic assemblages. The systematisation process carried out by these latter approaches has relatively helped to balance our level of knowledge regarding the quartz technology in comparison to that of the “traditional” raw materials, such as chert. (Ballin, 2008; de la Torre, 2004; de Lombera-Hermida et al., 2011; Driscoll, 2011b; Knutsson et al., 2015; Knutsson, 1988a; Mourre, 1997; Rodríguez-Rellán and Fábregas 2015; Tallavaara et al., 2010, *inter alia*).

In this sense, the session “New approaches to the study of Quartz lithic industries” held in Burgos (Spain) in the framework of the XVII World UISPP Congress was aimed to bring together the new advances and approaches to the technological, functional, economical and symbolical aspects of the quartz lithic assemblages from a wide geographical and chronological point of view. This issue follows the monographic character of the previous choral works edited by R. Barber (1981) or J. P. Bracco (1997b). Thus, the contributions presented here share the technological approach, focusing on the different aspects of the *chaîne opératoire*, from the raw material acquisition to the abandonment and postdepositional processes. Besides the technological, behavioural and economical significance of quartz, its social and symbolic sphere have also been considered, given their importance for understanding the relevance of this resource for the prehistoric societies.

Why Quartz.

One of the main issues in the scientific literature is the assumed “archaic” or poorly evolved character of the quartz assemblages (see Knutsson, 2014). This consideration lays mainly on the conjunction of three factors: 1) the particular mechanical and breakage patterns of quartz, which favour the poor formal standardization of the artefacts. 2) The predominant “flint-thinking” nature of the western Prehistoric Schools and, accordingly, the scarce formation and experience of the scholars in the study of non-flint records. 3) Finally, the strict application or interpretation of the traditional typologies to quartz lithic assemblages.

The difficulty of reading the quartz implements has definitely contributed to the misidentification and misclassification of quartz artefacts in the framework of the archaeological typologies, favouring –therefore– imprecise interpretations of the lithic assemblages (Driscoll, 2011a, 2011b; Lindgren, 1988; Tallavaara et al., 2010; Proffitt and de la Torre, 2014). For instance, a set of blind texts carried out by Byrne et al. (**this issue**) has highlighted the existence of an inter-analysts disagreement when assessing the technological and qualitative attributes of freehand and bipolar percussion on quartz knapping products.

In fact, the difficulty in the identification of the technical stigmas on quartz has fired up the controversy about the human origin of some quartz assemblages (Guidon et al., 1996; Meltzer et al., 1994; Pei, 1936) requiring, in some cases, additional experimental and taphonomic analysis prior to their approval by the scientific community (i.e. Boëda et al., 2014)

Quartz has been frequently regarded as a low quality raw material, its workability being limited by the presence of numerous internal flaws and cleavage planes (Bordes, 1947; Callahan, 1987). Besides its high fragmentation index, quartz presents a lower efficiency compared to that of other raw materials, producing a lower quantity of suitable cutting edges per unit mass (ie. Tallavaara et al., 2010). Quartz assemblages are generally defined by the application of expedient knapping methods, flake-based technologies, bipolar-on-anvil reduction and a high percentage of informal flaking products. Consequently, these records present a low formal variability that may be seen as “simple” by untrained experts. From a typological and evolutionist point of view, this loss of morphological standardization has been considered, in some cases, as evidence of a technological regression or of a conservative character.

These specific features of quartz have led to some researches to plainly ask why this raw material was even used by the prehistoric groups. Beyond this simplistic view, the new approaches are contributing to build a more complete and precise picture of the technological and behavioural issues that lay behind the question “Why Quartz?”

- Which are the textural, fracture and mechanical features of the quartz knapping products and raw material varieties?
- To what extent does the lithological offer in a territory constraint the organization of hominines’ technology?
- Which are the technological and functional strategies carried out in order to overcome such theoretical constraints?
- Are there parallels between the evolution of the quartz management strategies and the technological, cognitive and cultural evolution of the Pleistocene and Holocene techno-complexes?

From uniformity to variability.

Quartz has been traditionally considered as a homogeneous group of raw materials, being usually classified into two main varieties: milky quartz and rock crystal. Only in those cases where high quality and exogenous varieties were identified a distinction was made, remarking its exceptionality (i.e. “greasy quartz”, “quartz à œil”, etc.) (Ballin, 2008; Duran and Soler, 2006). These classifications do not take into account, however, the mineralogical features and quartz formation processes that can have important implications on the chemical composition, fracture mechanisms and, therefore, to wear formation processes (see Ollé et al., **this issue**). For this reason, a systematization of the terminology was required in order to establish the criteria for describing and classifying the different mechanical and textural features of quartz (Driscoll, 2011a; Mourre, 1996; 1997).

From a mineralogical point of view, quartz can be divided into two broad groups: macrocrystalline quartz and cryptocrystalline quartz, the latter including varieties such as chert, flint, chalcedony, etc. In the literature, the term “quartz” usually refers to the macrocrystalline variety. This variety is, in turn, defined accordingly to its crystal habit: Automorphic quartz (Euhedral quartz, well-developed hexagonal crystal, generally named as “rock crystal” or “hyaline quartz” by the archaeologists) and Xenomorphic quartz (Anhedral quartz, polycrystalline aggregates with a massive texture, generally labelled as “milky quartz”, “grey quartz”, etc. regarding their colour and appearance) (Mourre, 1996).

Little attention has been paid to the quartz’s formation processes in the archaeological research. The environmental conditions of the quartz vein and crystal formation (temperature, pressure, host rock, chemical solution, etc.) determine its mechanical, thermoluminescent and chemical properties, which –in turn- have important archaeological implications (i.e. Bons, 2001; Farias and Watanabe, 2012; Kozłowski and Marcinowska, 2007). On one hand, the geochemical variability of the quartz formations becomes, to some extent, a traceable resource. On the other, the textural differences, even within the same quartz vein (Collina-Girard, 1997), determine the workability of the quartz blanks.

Despite the high chemical purity of quartz (Götze and Möckel, 2012), the application of geochemical analysis imported from the geologist discipline has allowed to conduct the first raw material provenance studies of quartz archaeological artefacts. Nevertheless, the traditional geochemical approaches still have a coarser resolution than those applied on other raw materials, such as chert or obsidian. Another methodological handicap is the high chemical variability among the quartz veins, which demands a finer survey and a higher sampling investment in order to precisely locate the exact quartz sources (ten Bruggencate et al., 2014; Thirault et al., 2016).

The study of the fluid inclusions on the automorphic quartzes through different analytical techniques (Microthermometry, Raman spectrometry) has proved to be a useful method for the understanding of the exploitation and circulation of rock crystal artefacts during the European Mesolithic and Neolithic (Cousseran, 2000, 2002; Cousseran et al., 1998; Halavínová and Prichystal, 2008; Přichystal, 2006; Sachanbiński et al., 2008). On the contrary, the research on xenomorphic quartz has received little attention due to the coarser definition of the traditional

geochemical approaches on this quartz group. Isotope and trace elements analyses have yielded interesting results (Meighan et al., 2003), highlighting the application of the secondary ion mass spectrometry (SIMS), more accurate, on pegmatite quartz (ten Bruggencate et al., 2013, 2014). For sure, they will become useful methods for the raw material procurement studies, both at a local and regional scale.

In the archaeological literature, the classification of quartz has usually been based on macroscopic features such as colour, texture and transparency, but without considering any mineralogical criteria. Only few surveys or samplings aimed at the characterization of the hydrothermal formations or secondary deposits available in a given territory have been carried out so far (i.e. Berruti et al. e.p.; Boëda et al., 2014; Cousseran et al., 2002; Delagnes, 2011; Flenniken, 1981). For this reason, quartz has been claimed as an immediate and local resource and no detailed information has been provided regarding the local resources, therefore, yielding a diffused and biased description of the procurement strategies of the prehistoric communities. In this sense, the contribution by Aubry et al. (this issue) carried out in the Côa River valley (Northeast Portugal) shows that the combination of systematic surveys, careful description of the hydrothermal and archaeological quartz varieties and the application of a genetic and petrologic classification (Fernandes and Raynal, 2006; Fernandes et al., 2008) can be a useful methodology for the understanding of the procurement and exploitation strategies of the local raw materials. However, as the authors recognize, petrologic and microscopic analysis are needed for a more complete and precise approach. When combined with the study of foreign and cryptocrystalline materials (Aubry et al., 2012), this kind of approach offers a complete and complex picture of the raw material management strategies implemented by the Upper Palaeolithic societies at both local and regional scales.

Other authors have established a macroscopic classification focused on the textural features of quartz. In this sense, the morpho-structural groups determined by C. Llana (Martínez and Llana, 1996) are defined by the presence or absence of two variables: grain (referred to the well-defined crystalline units) and plane (referred to the existence of internal flaws, crystallization planes, fractures, etc.). This classification is related to two of the most important variables affecting the workability of quartz: texture and homogeneity/continuity. On the contrary, the morpho-structural groups do not offer any information about the petrologic origin of the quartz varieties. Nevertheless, this classification makes possible to recognize the technological or economical criteria behind the selection of artefacts in accordance with the prevalence of the technical needs of the Pleistocene and Holocene societies (de Lombera-Hermida et al., 2016; Llana and Villar, 1996; Rodríguez-Rellán and Fábregas-Valcarce, 2015).

These works highlight the importance of the recognition and description of the quartz varieties present in an archaeological record, which allow understanding the technical choices that define the technological behaviour of the quartz-based assemblages in a more precise way.

Quartz fracture and use wear features.

One of the evidences of the late development of the research on quartz as stone tool is the general lack of knowledge regarding its basic mechanical properties that still exists among archaeologists nowadays. Most approaches to this issue have repeatedly pointed out how the specific physical and mechanical properties of quartz cause it to behave quite unpredictably during the knapping sequence (Andrefsky, 1998; Cotterell and Kamminga, 1990), usually leading to a high fracture rate and a fairly common presence of accidents, which would turn it into a poor quality raw material (Bordes, 1947; Callahan, 1979; Whittaker, 1995). This “bad reputation” (Cornelissen, 2003) is still firmly stuck in the minds of many archaeologists around the world.

This happens in spite of the remarkable efforts that have been made in the last decades in order to try to define and to accurately evaluate the effects that the physical specificities of quartz –such as its sometimes grainy structure, the presence of internal flaws and planes or the anisotropic nature of its crystals– would have had over the production (Callahan et al., 1992; Cotterell and Kamminga, 1990; de Lombera-Hermida, 2009; Driscoll, 2011b; Flenniken, 1981; Knutsson and Lindgren, 1999; Martínez and Llana, 1996; Mourre, 1996; Novikov and Radililovsky, 1990) and use (Derndarsky and Ocklind, 2001; Knutsson et al., 2015; K. Knutsson, 1988b) of the lithic assemblages made on this raw material. This common struggle has gradually led to the achievement of a more realistic consideration of the physical properties of quartz, qualifying the traditional view that considered them as almost an insurmountable barrier for the exploitation of this raw material.

The present issue represents a further step in this direction, providing new and valuable contributions dealing with different aspects of the physical or mechanical properties of quartz. This is the case of M. Manninen’s paper (Manninen, [this issue](#)), which evidences how such characteristics have an effective impact on the knapping process but suggesting –at the same time– that the prehistoric knappers would have been able to partially overcome the limitations imposed by the raw material through the modification of the morphology and size of the knapping products. Meanwhile, other contributions focus on how quartz’s particular characteristics would have also led to specific breakage patterns and surface modifications when subjected to post-depositional alterations, such as trampling (Driscoll et al., [this issue](#)) or other taphonomic processes (Venditti et al., [this issue](#)).

Still, there are many aspects regarding the mechanical behaviour of archaeological quartz that are not fully understood, such as the exact impact that anisotropy or cleavage would have had during the knapping. Given their complexity (Domanski et al., 1994), these characteristics cannot be analysed by using only the observational or experimental methodologies that are typical of lithic studies. Thus, it seems quite logic to take advantage of those mechanical tests capable of providing accurate definitions and measurements of the different mechanical properties of solids, most of which have already been used in disciplines such as engineering or geology for a long time.

In this sense and although there is a relatively long list of works that have applied mechanical tests to lithic raw materials (i.e. Braun et al., 2009b; Doelman et al., 2001; McPherron et al., 2014; Rodríguez-Rellán et al., 2011, *inter alia.*), only a few of them have included quartz among the sampled materials (Domanski et al., 1994; Purdy and Brooks, 1971). The results suggest that quartz shows a much higher variability or heterogeneity than other raw materials (Domanski et al., 1994), circumstance that would be related to the aforementioned unpredictability during the knapping that has been referred by the specialists during decades. Within this issue, the application of one of these mechanical tests –the Equotip Hardness tester– to different raw materials, including xenomorphic and automorphic quartz (Rodríguez-Rellán, [this issue](#)), has led to an initial quantification of the impact that anisotropy and internal discontinuities of quartz would have had in the progression of mechanical forces similar to those acting during the flaking. These results suggest that internal planes rather than anisotropy would have played a major role in explaining the variability showed by quartz, supporting the conclusions achieved by former approaches (Cotterell and Kamminga, 1990; Novikov and Radililovsky, 1990).

Quartz processes conchoidal as well as uneven fracture characteristics. The scarce development of the typical conchoidal marks on xenomorphic quartz implements has favoured their misclassification within the archaeological record. For a correct technological interpretation of the knapping products, several experimental works have been carried out in order to define the quartz breakage patterns (Callahan et al., 1992; Driscoll, 2011b; Knutsson and Lindgren, 1999; Tallavaara et al., 2010) and technical stigmata on freehand and bipolar percussion (i.e. Byrne et al. [this issue](#); de la Peña, 2015; de la Peña et al., 2013; de Lombera-Hermida, 2009; Knight, 1991; Mourre, 1996; Villar, 1991). Most of these works have focused on the xenomorphic quartz, highlighting the relationship between these stigmata and the textural characteristic of the quartz. Automorphic quartz presents more developed conchoidal features (bulbs, ripples, etc.) but, as N. Tardy et al. ([this issue](#)) have assessed in their experimentation, its appearance is highly determined by the knapping technique performed and the direction of the fracture plane and its orientation with respect to the longitudinal axis and main anisotropy directions of quartz crystals.

In light of these statements, the precise identification of the impact points, direction of the removals and, to a lesser extent, their diachrony allow a diacritic lecture of the knapping products and a correct interpretation of the reduction and shaping methods. These works, in fact, have helped to the correct definition and understanding of the technological strategies in quartz lithic assemblages.

The use-wear analysis has experimented a parallel trajectory to that described for the technological approaches but with an even slower and later development, boosted in the last years by the improvement of the optical techniques (Alonso and Mansur, 1986-1990; Broadbent and Knutsson, 1975; Clemente-Conte, 1997; Fullagar, 1986; Igreja, 2009; Lombard, 2011; Pant, 1989; Pignat and Plisson, 2000; Sussman, 1985, 1988, *inter alia*). This dynamic has been correlative to the increasing interest on the wear-studies on other non-flint raw materials (i.e. Clemente-Conte et al., 2014). Similarly, the pioneering research was developed

from necessity in those regions where quartz was the main raw material in the assemblages, such as Scandinavia, South America or France.

Once again, quartz presents some handicaps such as a high reflectivity, irregular topography of the surfaces (especially on xenomorphic and grainy quartz) and mechanical fracture peculiarities that prevented the direct projection of the flint-based observations in the use-wear analysis of this raw material. As the contributions of Ollé et al. (this issue) and Márquez et al., (this issue) show, its brittle behaviour hinders the formation of polish and plastic deformations (an important feature for flint wear) and, in intensively used artefacts, may even prevent the preservation of the wear features. Besides, as Venditti et al. (this issue) indicates, the post-depositional processes affecting the surfaces of quartz implements must be taken into account in order to correctly perform the use wear analysis, as they tend to present some morphological similarities with use related features and, therefore, equifinalities may occur (K. Knutsson and Lindé, 1990).

Since the beginning of the quartz use-wear studies, the Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) has proved to be a useful tool for overcoming the problems related to the metallurgical microscopes observations, allowing the identification and diagnosis of the wear features on quartz artefacts surfaces (Knutsson, 1986, 1988b; Sussman, 1985). However, with respect of the light reflected microscopes, there has been an important instrumental advance during the last years with the use of differential interference contrast (DIC) and extended focus applications. The Laser Scanning Confocal Microscope (LSCM) has been successfully used for the definition of surface and subsurface wear features on xenomorphic quartz (Derndarsky and Ocklind, 2001). Within this issue, the paper by Fernández and Ollé (this issue) has highlighted the effectiveness of the Optical Light Microscope with a Nomarski prism on automorphic quartz, obtaining higher resolution images that considerably improve the wear description for this raw material. The combination of different methods and approaches (combined use of optical light and scanning electron microscopes) with sequential experiments have revealed as an appropriate procedure to correctly define and understand the wear traces on quartz and quartzose artefacts (Borel et al., 2014; Ollé et al., this issue).

In this sense, as in the aforementioned case of the quartz petrological and mechanical characteristics and as Ollé et al. (this issue) claim, a systematic description and terminological standardization was needed in order to define the use wear features on quartz artefacts for understanding the technical (i.e. hafting, knapping technique) and functional activities in which quartz artefacts are embedded (Knutsson et al., 2015, this issue).

Quartz lithic assemblages and the organization of lithic technology.

Several works have dealt with the organization of the lithic technology and its relation to raw material availability and formal lithic production (i.e. Andrefsky, 1994; Eren et al., 2014; Manninen, 2014). As stated before, the lower formal standardization of the quartz assemblages has favoured their consideration as expedient assemblages, defined by a low technical and knowledge investment. Conversely, the experimental and techno-economic studies have defined several

scenarios in which quartz, according to its status and abundance, plays different roles in the prehistoric technologies, overcoming the assumed mere substitutive character of this raw material (Bracco, 1996; 1997a, 1997b; Jaubert, 1997; Knutsson et al., 2015; Manninen and Knutsson, 2014). The different contributions gathered in this issue show a wide range of technological adaptive strategies aimed at overcoming the mechanical and technical peculiarities of quartz.

In this sense, the sites yielding long diachronic stratigraphic sequences, such as A Foz do Medal, in Northeast Portugal (Gaspar et al., [this issue](#)), or those regions with a long and relatively continued occupation, such as Northeast Iberia (Rodríguez-Álvarez, [this issue](#)) and the Côa Valley (Aubry et al., [this issue](#)), reflect the different ways in which the operative schemes of the Palaeolithic communities are adapted to the different techno-complexes requirements and the lithological offer. However, as the contribution of Knutsson et al., ([this issue](#)) state, these strategies and evolution are best observed during the pioneer colonization processes of territories devoid of fine-grained raw materials, giving the chance to trace the technical choices and technological adaptations of the prehistoric communities to the raw material availability. These studies also notice that not only the lithological context must be taken into account, but also its interaction with group mobility strategies and their cultural and technological backgrounds (Aubry et al., 2012; Bracco, 1996; Manninen and Knutsson, 2014).

One of the first changes in the technological basis of the prehistoric groups is related to their raw material procurement strategies. The lithic raw material diversification implies a widening of the raw material base to include locally accessible lithic resources (Manninen and Knutsson, 2014). The research on Northeast Portugal demonstrate that, for the Upper Paleolithic societies, it may also entail a higher investment in the survey of the local lithic resources of a territory leading to the discovery of new silicifications which are later integrated in their panoply (Aubry et al, [this issue](#); Gaspar et al., [this issue](#)). In parallel, the discovery of primary and secondary outcrops broadens the variability of the quartz resources and allows the improvement of the quality of the quartz's blanks.

The election of local quartz must not only be understood in the basis of its manufacture, workability or efficiency, but also in the basis of its utilisation (Douglass et al., [this issue](#)). In that sense, we must remember that both the macrocrystalline and cryptocrystalline varieties (cherts, calcedonies, etc.) of quartz have the same value of in Mohs Hardness scale (7) and, therefore, a similar theoretical efficiency in terms of use. Despite the high fragmentation index of the quartz knapping products, there is certain predictability in the way quartz fractures (Callahan et al., 1992; Tallavaara et al., 2010), allowing the obtaining of some foreseeable morphologies and a wide range of morphologies and sizes.

Although the mechanical properties of quartz may determine the knapping methods and techniques at a first stage, Douglass et al. ([this issue](#)) point that the selection and transport of the quartz knapping products according to the utilisation criteria is an effective strategy to overcome such constraints. Contrary to the general consideration of the expedient and immobile character of the quartz lithic industries, the spatial fragmentation of the *chaînes opératoires* and the

distant transport of selected quartz artefacts has been documented in various archaeological records (Moncel et al., 2008) and even some quartz artefacts (specially bifacial points) have behaved as true *curated tools* for high residential mobility groups (Holdaway and Douglass, 2015; ten Bruggencate et al., 2014).

In this sense, we must bear in mind that, for the prehistoric knappers, the primary selection criterion was the sharp edges and their durability, but not necessarily the formality of the tools (Braun et al., 2009a; Knutsson, 2014). This can be actually observed in the use of small-unmodified flakes and flakes fragments as cutting tools or embedded in composite tools, as the functional analyses have proven (Igreja, 2009; Knutsson et al. 2015, [this issue](#); Knutsson, 1988b). The study of the quartz implements from Navalmaíllo rock shelter (Spain) show that these artefacts play a versatile function within the subsistence strategies of Neanderthal groups, and the use of Siret fragments or unmodified flakes was not random (Márquez et al.). Thus, the functional efficiency of the quartz edges must be understood as one of the main factors that explains the wide utilization of this raw material, rather than its workability alone.

As stated before, the anisotropy nature of the automorphic quartz and the important presence of the cleavage and internal flaws on xenomorphic quartz are considered as the main limiting factors for its workability (Rodríguez-Rellán, [this issue](#)). Accordingly, in quartz assemblages several technical choices have been documented in order to overcome (and also to take advantage of) these breakage characteristics. The comparative study made by Manninen ([this issue](#)) show that some of these strategies are commonly employed by quartz knappers across a wide chronological and geographical span. The different archaeological records reflect some of the technical solutions, such as the production of flakes with larger platform areas in order to produce thicker elements and, therefore, avoid the fragmentation of the detachments (Manninen, [this issue](#); Tallavaara et al., 2010, Driscoll, 2011b); the preferential use of neocortical alluvial surfaces as striking platforms; the application of knapping methods based on longitudinal reduction sequences on the xenomorphic quartz cores (Bisson, 1990; de Lombera-Hermida et al., 2011; Rankama et al., 2006; Rodríguez-Rellán and Valcarce, 2015); and the use of bipolar-on-anvil percussion.

Among them, the bipolar-on-anvil reduction has been considered as one of the most widespread techniques for reducing the fragmentation of the knapping products and providing greater efficiency in terms of cutting edge length per mass (Bordes, 1947; Díez-Martín et al., 2011; Gurtov and Eren, 2014). The archaeological record show that this technique is widely applied on quartz assemblages (de Lombera-Hermida et al., 2016; Prous et al., 2009-2010) focused on the production of flakes and, also, microliths for composite tools (de la Peña and Wadley, 2014; Klaric, 2009). Several authors have dealt with the bipolar-on-anvil percussion and the definition of its knapping features, either from a statistical or qualitative point of view (i.e. de la Peña, 2015; de la Torre et al., 2013; Díez-Martín et al., 2010, 2011), although there is some variability among the results of these studies. Within this issue, the experimentation made by Byrne et al., ([this issue](#)) points that a similar proportion of complete flakes, fragmented flakes and angular chunks are produced through freehand and bipolar percussion. Besides, no

significant morphometric differences can be stated between their knapping products, underlining the importance of their qualitative attributes for a correct interpretation.

Another technological strategy developed by prehistoric knappers is the differential management of the raw material resources according to their availability, texture, quality and workability as it is generally asserted, for example, for several Middle, Upper Paleolithic and Late Prehistoric records (Aubry et al., [this issue](#); de Lombera-Hermida et al., 2011; Gaspar et al., [this issue](#); Geneste and Turq, 1997; Huet, 2007; Jaubert, 1997; Jaubert & Farizy, 1995; Rodríguez-Álvarez, [this issue](#); Rodríguez-Rellán and Valcarce, 2015). On one hand, in quartz based assemblages, the expedient reduction strategies are generally applied for flake production, and the shaping sequences are focused on small flakes tools (especially denticulate group), usually on the xenomorphic variety. On the other hand, formal technologies (Levallois, blade and bladelet production) are preferentially made on fine-grained and other raw materials (flint, quartzite, tuff, basalt, etc).

Nevertheless, there can be some reinterpretations of the formal technologies as a response to the mechanical constraint of quartz, yielding the emergence of particular *chaînes opératoires*. One of the best known examples is the specific reduction methods applied on automorphic quartz for blade and bladelet production in the Upper Palaeolithic, Mesolithic and Neolithic societies (i.e. Chelidonio, 1990; Fabián, 1984-1985; García and Ziáurriz, 1997; Honegger, 2001; Ramil and Ramil, 1997). The Upper Palaeolithic levels from Foz do Medal site (Gaspar et al., [this issue](#)) show that the reduction method of the automorphic quartz take advantage of the natural morphology of the crystals and of their anisotropy breakage planes for the production of bladelets and blanks for lithic barbs, which functional efficiency is similar to those made on flint or fine-grained raw materials (Rodríguez-Rellán et al., 2011). The experimentation carried out by N. Tardy ([this issue](#)) state that these products, techno-typologically similar to those documented on flint, can be obtained through the performance of several knapping techniques and methods, but always adapted to the anisotropic nature of automorphic quartz.

The differential exploitation of these resources and the appearance of specific *chaînes opératoires* on quartz show, again, the deep knowledge of the raw material mechanical features by the prehistoric knappers. However, these differential management strategies of the lithic resources must not be understood alone on the basis of raw material categories, but in the basis on raw material qualities (Meignenn, 1988). When good quality quartz blanks were available and selected, complex reduction and shaping methods could be performed. Although scarce evidences are documented, as the example from Cardina I shown in [this issue](#) (Aubry et al., [this issue](#)), there are some examples of Levallois knapping products on good quality xenomorphic quartz varieties (Duran and Soler, 2006; Fábregas et al., 2012; Jaubert and Farizy, 1995; Mourre, 1996; Rodríguez-Álvarez, 2004). Exceptionally, blade and bladelet production on quite homogeneous xenomorphic quartz has been reported in some Pleistocene and Holocene records (Ballin, 2008; de Lombera-Hermida et al., 2012; Zilhão et al., 1997).

As stated by Knutsson et al., ([this issue](#)) in those regions where good quality raw material is scarce or absent there is usually a simplification of the technology as a flexible and adaptive strategy to the environmental conditions. On quartz assemblages, defined by a flake-based technology, it can lead to a certain formal homogenization of the archaeological records. From a diachronic point of view, it can give the impression of a certain *continuum* and morphotechnical similarity (Jaubert, 1997), which some authors consider as prove of the existence regional techno-cultural traditions (Garcia Garriga, 2011; Rankama et al, 2006). However, other authors (i.e. Rodríguez-Álvarez, [this issue](#)) claim that these common adaptive strategies may produce a change in the operational schemes of the prehistoric groups in order to adapt their technology to the lithological conditions, but not necessary imply a major change of the conceptual scheme. When good quality materials are available, even in scarcity (flint, fine-grained quartzite, etc.), formal technologies on these materials are similar to those identified in those territories with fine-grained raw materials (Barsky, 2013; Rodríguez-Álvarez, [this issue](#); Jaubert and Farizy, 1995; Knutsson et al., [this issue](#); Aubry et al., [this issue](#); Gaspar et al., [this issue](#)).

When we regard to other spheres of the archaeological record, the conceptual complexity of the prehistoric societies is usually equivalent to those cultural groups settled in neighbouring territories supplied with good quality resources. The development of specific operational schemes in quartz-based assemblages reflects the flexibility and habituation of the human groups to the constraints of their territories. But these changes in the operational schemes do not necessarily imply a change or simplification of the technological, social, or even cultural basis as it is reflected in other technological and behavioural strategies regarding to raw material supply (Aubry et al., 2012; Geneste and Turq, 1997), transport (Douglass, et al., [this issue](#), Holdoway and Douglass, 2015), lithic technology (i.e. de Lombera-Hermida et al., 2011, 2016; Faivre et al., 2013; Jaubert, 1997; Rodríguez-Álvarez, [this issue](#)), bone technology (Knutsson et al., 2015, [this issue](#)), and even in the symbolic, artistic and cultural spheres (T. Aubry, 2009; Fábregas et al., 2015).

Quartz symbolic roles

Besides its strictly utilitarian use, quartz had also played a deep symbolic role during prehistory. Such significance is especially marked in the case of the prismatic crystals of automorphic quartz, which have been repeatedly linked to ritual uses. Some of the physical characteristics of quartz crystals –such as their translucent character, their iridescence and ability to decompose the light in several colours, or their triboluminescence, which make them shine when rubbed or struck against another crystal– might be the origin of such special nature (Reynolds, 2009; Taçon, 1991).

The use of quartz and rock crystal as more than mere raw material might have started in the Lower and, more likely, the Middle Palaeolithic, when unmodified prisms may have been collected as non-utilitarian objects (D'Errico et al., 1989; Moncel et al., 2012). However, it is after the introduction of the agriculture when this symbolic role seems to have reached its peak. Thus, unmodified quartz

crystals were systematically included as part of the grave goods in hundreds of Neolithic mounds of –among other places– Portugal, Spain, France and the British Isles (Cassen, 2000; Darvill, 2002; Fábregas, 1983; Forteza et al., 2009; Fowler and Cummings, 2003), including magnificent specimens –such as the 20 cm. long smoky quartz crystal of the dolmen of Alberite (Cádiz, Spain) (Ramos and Giles, 1996)– or large sets, as in La Veguilla I (Salamanca, Spain), where 73 intact crystals have been referred (Soler Díaz, 1991). This link between unmodified rock crystals and megalithic mounds suggests a possible funerary nature of this kind of items. In this sense, an analysis of more than 200 sites in Western Iberia with rock crystal artefacts evidenced how the 97% of the unmodified prisms were recovered in funerary contexts (Rodríguez-Rellán, 2010).

The reason for including intact crystals of quartz among the funerary grave goods is difficult to assess. One might argue that they were deposited there simply as a supply of raw material for being used in the afterlife; in this sense, the fact that transformed rock crystal (as cores, flakes and blades, arrowheads, etc.) has also been frequently recovered inside burials (Bueno Ramírez, 1988; Forteza González et al., 2009; Garrido Cordero, 2015) might point in that direction. Sometimes, however, quartz was not a local raw material and it was not regularly used by the human groups in the area, so the crystals included in the grave goods would have travelled hundreds of kilometres along the exchange networks (Ramos and Giles, 1996), circumstance that may be seen as an evidence of their social and symbolic significance.

In their attempts for understanding the symbolic role that quartz had during the prehistory, archaeologists (Darvill, 2002; Reynolds, 2009) have echoed the massive number of ethnographic references stressing the ritual and apotropaic importance that this mineral have had for human groups all around the world, even in current Western European societies (Quintía, 2015). Thus, quartz was believed to have and convey magic or healing power (Eliade, 1995) and, therefore, it has been repeatedly linked to shamans and shamanistic practices (Dickau et al., 2013; VanPool, 2009). Quartz crystals would have allowed or facilitated the communication with the world of the spirits and they had a significant role in the episodes of transformation, such as the initiation ceremonies (Reynolds, 2009). It may be due to its double value as communication channel and vehicle of transformation that quartz was included in the funerary contexts, scene of the ultimate transformation of the human being. Burying a corpse together with quartz crystals or quartz chunks would have allowed the living to “keep in touch” with the new-dead member of the community, who could act as mediator before the ancestors or spirits.

But not only rock crystals would have been imbued of this special significance, vein quartz –in the form of cobbles or simple blanks or chunks– was repeatedly used as building material in many European megaliths. Its use would have been a method for increasing the perceptibility of these monuments in the landscape (Bradley et al., 2000; Tilley, 1996) but also a way of transmitting a complex set of ideas (Darvill, 2002; Fowler and Cummings, 2003).

This value may have also been transferred to the transformed objects. A perfect example of this can be seen in the paper by A. Morgado and colleagues (Morgado et al. **this issue**), focused on the analysis of the rock crystal assemblages recovered in several Copper Age sites of Southern Iberia. These include some of the most spectacular examples of rock crystal artefacts in Western Europe, such as a dagger blade and very finely crafted arrowheads. The difficulties imposed by the raw material might have acted as a stimulus and an opportunity for the artisans to display their abilities, so the objects would have had a double value: that originated by the technical expertise or know-how necessary to cope with the complexity of their manufacture and the one derived from the significance or symbolism of the raw material itself.

Conclusions

Quartz is one of the most used raw materials for stone-tool production by the prehistoric communities. Its presence is not only constrained to those territories avoid of fine-grained and good quality materials. Its wide availability and hardness may explain its broad utilisation since the earliest stages of the Human Technology. The technological approach to the study of the quartz lithic assemblages developed during the last decades, has shown that quartz play different and significant roles within the technological strategies of the Plesitocene and Holocene communities.

The mechanical and physical features of quartz have determined the technology and functionality of the lithic assemblages, but several strategies (including specific *chaînes opératoires*) were performed in order to adapt to their different techno-complexes requirements. On the contrary, its particular mechanical, textural, morphological and functional properties have favoured its utilisation in determined socio-economic and functional contexts, becoming it a versatile resource. In addition, they have even awarded quartz with new simbological and anthropopaic meanings by the prehistoric societies.

Consequently, quartz assemblages –despite being at first glance under the appearance of a certain formal homogeneization– show a wider technological variability and complexity than previsouly thought. It that sense, the new approaches have overcome the preconceptions regarding its emergency resource status and the archaism and scant evolved character of these lithic assemblages. When we look into the technological strategies developed on quartz assemblages (mainly their adaptation to quartz mechanical features) and also to other aspects of the archaeological record (other fine-grained raw materials, bone industry, art, etc.) we can recongize the high technological and and behavioural complexity of these communities.

Quartz assemblages reflect the high knowledge of the lithological availability of a territory, the particular mechanical and functional features of this raw material and the development by the prehistoric societies of complex and varied technical and adaptive strategies to the lithic resources and environmental constraints. In

that sense, they can be considered as prove of the high, flexibe and adpatative character of the prehistoric societies.

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